

Circulation, “Incoherence” and Empire: Revisiting Two Approaches in Recent Historical Writings on Colonial Northeast India

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In the recent times, two approaches which have shaped some significant studies on colonial Northeast India are: the idea of incoherence of empire, and circulatory networks or circulation. Highlighting the conceptual departures they contain, this article is also an attempt to revisit the two approaches by drawing attention to some of the broader questions that these approaches need to take into account. For example, vis-à-vis the region, how does the idea of incoherence or that of circulation extend the understanding of imperial accumulation of power and capital at a global scale. Further, if structuring of areas in imperial processes operates at different spatial scales, then how does de-centring these scales (as in the two approaches) enable one to identify what is imperialism as far as the region is concerned. The two approaches of incoherence of empire and circulation have also foregrounded the question of highlands. As such, the article argues that coherence or incoherence could have different loci. While at one level, certain areas of the region (whether plains, foothills or highlands) could be understood in terms of empire’s coherence there could be other areas, especially highlands, which tend to exhibit features of relative incoherence in this regard. However, as the chapter argues, if the vantage point of examination is empire and the fact of its presence (however limited or informal), then is it possible to look into combinations of processes to understand how such combinations could be oriented towards imperial accumulation of power (and capital) across these different kinds of areas that comprised colonial Northeast India.

Keywords: Colonial Northeast India, British Assam, Incoherence of empire, Circulatory networks, highlands, Frontier, tea, Capitalist logic.

Introduction

Historical scholarship examines and makes history meaningful through certain ideas and concepts. In this regard, two recent approaches which have shaped some significant studies on colonial Northeast India are: the idea of incoherence of empire, and circulation. While highlighting the conceptual departures of these approaches,

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this article is also an attempt to revisit these approaches by drawing attention to some of the broader questions that they could possibly take into account as well. For example, vis-à-vis the ideas of incoherence and that of circulation, how does its de-centred understanding of empire extend our understanding of imperial accumulation of power and capital at a global scale. Further, if structuring of areas in imperial processes operates at different spatial scales, then how does de-centring these scales enable one to identify what is imperialism as far as the region is concerned.

In order to examine these issues, the article is divided into two sections. The first section examines the conceptual departures of the idea of incoherence of empire and that of circulation. In the process, the section also revisits some of the aspects of colonialism which have not attracted the attention of two approaches, especially questions of imperial accumulation of power and capital. A point which is noted in the section is that historicising highlands shows how different highland areas had different experiences of empire and capital. Extending this discussion, the second section argues, if the vantage point of examination is empire and the fact of its presence (however limited or informal), then is it possible to look into combinations of processes to understand how such combinations could be oriented towards imperial accumulation of power (and capital) across different kinds of areas stretching from the plains to foothills and the highlands. In other words, if our area of study is conceived thus, it can reveal the underlying logic of empire and capital. In turn, circulation also becomes an interesting and crucial framework to examine the underlying logic, and in that respect, certain dimensions of colonial Northeast India.

A departure in recent historical scholarship

A good starting point to examine the conceptual departures contained in the two approaches (incoherence of empire and circulation) would be to begin with an earlier body of post-colonial scholarship which was premised on the idea of empire as an organsied structure of power and capital. This earlier scholarship focused on the relations between colonial institutions and colonial socio-economic conditions as far as colonial Northeast India is concerned. In fact, the relation between institutions and socio-economic conditions were of primary concern for the colonial state too. For example, the voluminous writings on the region that fill the archives, such as on land administration, trade, political movements, police, tea, agriculture, minerals, banking and credit, etc., besides the different royal commissions of enquiry from time to time, is a testimony to the colonial interest in this regard. However, when we compare this nature of colonial interest with the one to be found in the earlier post-colonial historical scholarship, especially between the 1950s and 1980s, one can notice a marked shift. The shift is that this earlier post-colonial historical scholarship was shaped by the anti-colonial attitude. As a result, their examination of institutions (colonial or traditional) and socio-economic conditions is guided by the sense of critique of colonialism. It is also in this intellectual context that certain ideas and concepts assumed importance in these works.

For example, two prominent historians of this period are H.K. Barpujari (1912-2002) and Amalendu Guha (1924-2015). In the works of H.K. Barpujari (2007a; 2007b), colonial

institutions such as land and revenue administration, state and its bureaucratic apparatus (both in the plain districts and the hill districts of colonial Assam), the later representative bodies, etc., as well as material life in terms of socio-economic conditions, are approached in terms of the structures produced by the colonial state. Notably, these structures are studied as part of both forms of dominance as well as of a top-down transformation (effected in the region). In the works of Amalendu Guha (2014a; 2014b), institutions (especially in terms of colonial land and revenue administration, colonial law making) or relations of the peasants and the working class with the colonial state/tea plantation regime are primarily approached through the conceptual framework of mode of production. The argument is that, when colonialism is approached in terms of the framework of mode of production, one can see how there is a greater reproduction of inequality and distress due to the political and economic relations instituted under colonialism. In the case of studies on the Brahmaputra valley, this earlier post-colonial trend of historical scholarship seems to have continued into the contemporary times too (for example, Sharma, 2012; Saikia, 2014; Goswami, 2012). This continuity is basically in terms of recognising the empire as a concrete process of dominance, as an institutionalised practice of unequal relation of power between the colonial master and the colonised subject. It has also meant that colonialism comprised a concrete economic process which generally produced impoverishment and economic distress for the masses, especially due to the land and revenue policies, as well as through the manner in which British capitalist profit was secured. It is also in this regard that the role of colonial forms of violence is studied.

However, vis-à-vis the above lines of enquiry on colonial Northeast India, a body of recent historical scholarship suggests an alternative framework. The two ideas that significantly inform this emerging framework are those of incoherence of empire and that of circulatory networks. These ideas, which have been applied globally too, is mainly about de-centring the understanding of empire. For example, with regard to the idea of incoherence, it is generally argued in such studies that contrary to the British empire being a coherent system, “incoherence was the essence of empire” (Wilson and Dilley 2023: 191-217). The “incoherence” is about the multiplicity and contradictions in forms and practices that characterised the empire, or the limits to knowing or governing the colonised that marked the empire (Ballantyne, 2010: 429-452, Simpson, 2021). In other words, what incoherence means here is that, rather than being about structures of power and dominance based on the interests of the metropole, the empire actually needs to be approached as an open-ended process of interactions, circulations, negotiations and exchanges between different regions and societies of the trans-geographical imperial world. In the recent times, such an idea of incoherence of empire has been applied with regard to colonial Northeast India as well (Simpson, 2021; Jackson, 2016). For example, based on studies of the colonial projects of infrastructure, it is argued that while, “an internal cohesion via an infrastructure of control was sought from the start” (Jackson, 2016: 41), this control was never achieved, or remained liminal. It is also in this regard that the idea of incoherence comes to share an interesting relation with the idea of circulatory networks (of routes, goods and people), as applied in the case of the region. For example, a significant point about circulatory networks

that is emphasised is that these networks exceeded or transcended the structures of colonial control, thereby highlighting the limits of these structures (Dzuvichu, 2019: 237-261; Pachua, 2022: 105-136). This lack of control (and thereby, a certain unknowability of the subject and the region for colonial institutions and the colonial agents) is reflected in the different instances of colonial anxieties over both knowing as well as controlling the frontier.

When viewed vis-à-vis the earlier historical scholarship, as mentioned before, one may argue that the departure in this recent body of scholarship is at two levels. First, since the geographical core of these studies are the highlands, they provide a framework through which the nature of colonialism, when viewed from such spaces, can be examined afresh. That is, terms such as “hill districts”, “partially administered” areas, “unadministered” areas, etc., through which the highlands of the colonial Northeast India were generally characterised, and which have also tended to refer to a particular nature or formation of colonial institutions and socio-economic conditions in the highlands, need not be understood through ideas of exception. Rather, when compared to the Assam plains, the evidently limited institutional presence of the empire in these highlands (such as, in terms of land administration, law, or the police, etc.), as well as the dynamic trans-regional nature of the circulatory networks wherein the nature of colonial power could be more diffused, fit into a global essence of the British empire itself – its general incoherence.

This also brings one to the second level of significance of this body of studies. Namely, they open up the idea of the colonial subject, and that of agency of the subject, in new ways. Such as, if power is diffused and limited, and if a community/social group can operate at a trans-regional level, then it not only refers to a situation of multiple subject conditions, but also that the subject can actually shift its location/positioning in multiple regimes, depending on the context at hand. When viewed thus, it makes it possible to study the highlands beyond categories or processes which are otherwise connected to or emanates from the institution of state (i.e., the colonial state). As would be evident, such an understanding of relation between subject, agency and power has important implications in the conceiving of what constitutes institutions and socio-economic conditions in the colonial context, and thereby to our understanding of popular responses to colonialism as well. For example, as shown in the case of the colonial Lushai Hills district, the very sites of colonial power (such as, forced labour in road building in order to expand or entrench colonial power) could actually also be sites of escape from colonial power (and thereby the limits to colonial power) due to the underlying incoherence (i.e., the actuality of its diffused and non-systemic nature on the ground). The circulatory networks that exceed colonial control, and of which such sites become part of (Jackson, 2016: 39-71; Jackson, 2024) make the above further possible. Thereby, in reality, the colonial state comes to exist as some kind of a liminal phenomenon not only in terms of its institutions, but also in terms of the extent to which it conditions or regulates the socio-economic life of the highlands. This point is important because it allows one to examine social realities beyond the sphere of the state.

While recognising the important conceptual departures that mark the above studies, one also needs to note that there continues to be studies on the colonial highlands of

the region which seem to view the matter differently. For example, there are contemporary studies which argue that limits of control do not necessarily mean the absence of colonial structure of power and dominance, including in the highlands (May, 2016: 5-20).¹ Such as, studies show how in the highlands the nature of changing land relations, customary forms or ideas of customary rights actually take shape through the centrality and mediation of colonial institutions (such as, of law and administration), not outside of these institutions (Karlsson, 2011: 126-172). In other words, as these studies argue, institutions of land relations or what comprises customary is now repositioned through, not outside of, what the colonial state sees and recognises. Besides, with regard to the circulatory networks of the foothills and highlands in the colonial period, studies have argued that the older networks across such spaces were in fact “redesigned” during the period into a new pattern that mainly fitted into the interests of colonial power and commerce (Saikia, 2022: 137-163). Such “redesigning”, it is argued, fundamentally impacted the foothill and highland communities too, both politically and socio-economically.

Studies have also argued that the issue to examine, with regard to the highlands, is not necessarily whether its colonial forms are similar to those of the plains. Rather, one needs to focus on the nature of the restructuring of institutions and practices of authority, the disruptions in modes of economic life, as well as the institutionalising of cultural discourses (such as, the “primitive”) in political, economic or legal governance; all of these being dimensions of colonial governmentality wherein the locus of power remains with the colonial state (Misra, 2024). It is pointed out that the disguising of power is not the absence of power; and that when viewed thus, the forms and extent of popular resistances in the highlands against these dimensions of colonial governmentality can also be better appreciated (i.e., they too comprised a form of anti-colonial resistance due to the reality of colonialism). Interestingly, as these studies show, colonial discourse itself tended to represent these resistances as “primitive” outbursts due to colonialism’s liminal presence in these spaces (Misra, 2024). In this regard, though not on colonial Northeast India but on the colonial Burma frontier (which include highlands), studies have interestingly demonstrated how circulatory networks exceeding the limits of colonial control need not actually mean the limits of the colonial state. Rather, it is the underlying relation between colonial private capital and the colonial state – through which the frontier is structured into imperial processes – which explains the disguised, diffused or indirect presence of the state in the frontier (Tagliacozzo, 2007). Therefore, this condition is not the same as what the idea of liminal presence of the colonial state stands for. As such, one may argue that these studies highlight the need to approach the circulatory networks in terms of the idea of regimes of network, rather than approaching the networks as forms of open-ended flows. It means there is a location of power in circulatory networks, and the disguised, diffused or indirect presence of the state in the frontier is an imperial form, not the lack of its substance. (This point is again discussed in the second section of this article. For an interesting analysis of the point, also see, Cooper, 2001: 189-213). One may also argue that these studies thereby caution us to be careful about essentialising a stateless or escaping-the-state condition wherein histories and practices are deemed beyond the mind and the practical reach of the colonial state.

Coherence of empire and Circulatory networks

Thus, with regard to highlands of the region, what we find is that there are actually two frameworks in recent studies – one of empire’s incoherence and in that sense circulation, and the other of empire’s coherence (though disguised or discoursed by the colonial state in languages of liminality) and circulation as part of that regime. But can this apparent duality be approached differently, by making the logic of accumulation of power and capital by empire on a global scale as our reference in order to explain why should imperialism not be equated to one given form? For example, with regard to the region, how would one understand the issue of capital accumulation, the reorganising and rescaling of different societies and geographies of the world at different global scales, and the connection of the colonial state to such a process of reorganising and rescaling. A body of earlier scholarship in different world contexts points out that capital accumulation does not necessarily require a pre-given condition in order to realise the accumulation. The necessary condition for the accumulation can also be produced, and it is here that the role of the colonial state (i.e., power) becomes crucial. Further, the necessary condition does not imply sameness across societies and geographies. As long as existing conditions, whatever they may be, can be rearticulated towards the reproduction of capital and power, it fulfils the general logic of the process (Binsbergen and Geschiere, (1985)2011; Stoler, 1995). One of the significant factors that create the condition of the rearticulation as well as its reproduction is the colonial state. All this not only means that capitalism and colonialism comprised a conjoined process. It also means that the peculiarity of the process is precisely its reproduction through the structuring and rescaling of different kinds of societies, economies and regions at a global level. This structuring and rescaling do not mean homogenisation of/in the colonial worlds. Rather, it is about how these differences become harnessed to a conjoined process of the reproduction of both colonial power and capital accumulation. This actuality of multiplicity in/through which such a process realises itself is understood as the nature of the capitalist-imperialist logic of the times.²

With regard to colonial Northeast India, this conjoined nature of the capitalism and colonialism can be illustrated through an example from one of its formative moments itself. The example pertains to something as basic as what the idea of “discovery” of tea in Assam meant for the colonial agents in the 1830s and early 1840s, and how the tea plant-commodity was perceived in terms of empire and capital during the period. What such examples allow us to see is how societies, economies, geographies (hills, plains, foothills), plants and even forms of existing knowledge are organised through new institutions (such as, botanical gardens, administrative mechanisms, bodies of research and experiments, and the military), and in the process, how they are rescaled through circulatory networks that are at the levels of global accumulation of capital and power.

The correspondences of the Proceedings of the Agricultural Society of India (Correspondence Regarding the Discovery of the Tea Plant of Assam), 1841, comprises a series of letters written in the 1820s and 1830s, references to the British Parliamentary papers on tea, and the presentations made before the Agricultural Society of India in 1841, all pertaining to who should be credited with the “discovery” of tea in Assam.

What is interesting is that the matter of “discovery” of tea in Assam came up in 1841 when the credit (the “gold medal”) for it had already been given to Charles A. Bruce by the British government. The matter came up because Andrew Charlton raised objection to it and presented his case before the Society, that it is he who should have been given the credit (the “gold medal”) for the same. Charlton was In-charge of tea in Assam until 1835,³ when he recommended Charles A. Bruce as the Overseer of the Tea plantations in Assam. Charlton then left Assam to recover from an injury. Charlton’s case opened a fierce debate in the Society as well as in the English press, and in the process of the debates, a range of documents (letters, Parliamentary papers, views of the Press) as well as opinions of the members of the Society came forth, and were compiled. Eventually, the Society (though not the British government) came to a conclusion that it is Charlton who deserves the credit of “discovery”. The process of the debates also brought forth the role of Nathaniel Wallich, who was then the Superintendent of the Botanical Garden of Calcutta. Based on the letters he had written between 1832 and 1838 to various officers of the East India Company, the Society, and to the British government, it turned out that he had given the credit for the “discovery” of tea in Assam to different individuals at different points of time, such as to Andrew Charlton, to Francis Jenkins, to David Scott, and lastly to Charles A. Bruce. Wallich had eventually recommended the name of Charles A. Bruce for the “gold medal”.

Interestingly, in his representations to the Society, Charlton points out, “The tea plant of Assam, I am well aware, was known to most of the intelligent natives of the country, and the different wild tribes in the vicinity of Suddyah and Beesa were all more or less in the habit of drinking an infusion of the leaves before any European ever went into the Province” (Correspondence, 1841: 10)⁴. This point of Charlton found its way into animated discussions in the English press of the times too (Correspondence, 1841: 62-63). In other words, Charlton’s claim is not that he is the first to observe on the possibility of tea already growing in Assam. His claim is that he is first to experiment and bring it to public notice (by which he means the East India Company, the Government, and the Press) that Assam can produce the “genuine tea of commerce”. For example, regarding tea growing in Assam, he remarks, “No one knew it was the genuine tea of commerce, or took any effective measures to prove it was so, prior to my communication to the Agri.-Horticultural Society in February 1832.” (Correspondence, 1841: 10) In a rejoinder to Wallich in 1841, he further points out that even though in 1825 David Scott might have sent to Wallich the leaves and seeds of tea from Assam, “*He had not seen it manufactured into potable tea* (emphasis in original); and no one (as Captain Wilcox states in his letter to Dr. Spry, read at the Society’s last Meeting) ventured to entertain a hope that the tough leaved plant of the jungles could be prepared to resemble Chinese tea. By experiment on experiment I at last succeeded at making so good sample.” (Correspondence, 1841: 43) This, as Charlton points out in his many communications, is not a reference merely to the tea plant, but to the “tea of commerce”, i.e., the tea that could be a commodity to be produced within the Indian domain of the East India Company vis-à-vis Chinese tea.

It is in such a context that he also notes, “I claimed, and *do* (emphasis in original) claim the *merit* (emphasis in original) from the circumstance of my having been the first to

communicate the discovery to the public through the medium of the Agricultural Society of India, and afterwards in the official organ of the Government, the *Government Gazette* of March 12, 1832.” (Correspondence, 1841: 36) Writing on the issue, the English press, such as the *Q.E.D.*, put the matter as, “The tea plant *existed* (emphasis in original) in Assam prior to his [Capt. Charlton] discovery, or we verily think he never would have discovered that it *was* (emphasis in original) the tea plant; but though other men had heard of it, and seen it, and even scratched their heads about it, he alone proved it to be *the tea* (emphasis in original), and to him therefore is undoubtedly due the glory of having discovered that the tea of commerce was indigenous to Assam.” (Correspondence, 1841: 64) Notably, in his letter dated 6 December 1834, addressed to the Chairman and Members of the Tea Committee, Wallich had mentioned that, “I humbly submit that a more interesting, a more valuable fact, has never before been brought to light in Indian Agriculture, than has thus been established, beyond all dispute, by Lieut. Charlton.” (Correspondence, 1841: 4)

For our purposes, the important point here is that the colonial archive does not shy away from the fact that colonial institutions (i.e., the power they represent) cannot be meaningfully separated from the idea of capitalist profit (“tea of commerce”). In this regard, a tea memoir (Assam: Sketch, 1839) of the Assam Company (estb. February, 1839), also helps in illustrating how this “discovery” of the “tea of commerce” is fundamentally connected to the rescaling of the region at the global level. For example, the memoir points out in the beginning that its aim is to furnish information on Assam and Assam tea to the, “shareholders and others interested in the *Assam Company* (italics in original) lately established” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 1), and that, “it is intended for those who possess neither the time nor the means for referring to the documents, but who are nevertheless desirous of possessing some information on the grounds and the principles upon which the Assam Company is based and has been carried forward, and of the probable outturn of so interesting an adventure.” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 3-4) The sharing of the information is also aimed at highlighting how the colonial state, capitalist “private enterprise” and resources in “the most eastern limits of Her Majesty’s dominions in British India” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 5) are part of an organized global scale of relation that transcended any particular region or society.

For example, pointing to one of the constituents of the relation, i.e. soil, the memoir notes, “Looking to the general soil of Assam – which is described to be of extraordinary fertility... under a more settled government than it has possessed for the last century, this province will prove a highly valuable acquisition to the British government.” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 13) This sets the stage for comparing “tea soils” from Assam and China. The comparison, as the memoir notes, provide the following information, “The two peculiarities in these soils are, the first, that they contain no carbonate of lime, and only traces of phosphate and sulphate; and the next, that their iron is almost wholly in the state of carbonate of iron, a widely different compound from the simple oxides. They would be called poor yellow loams, and cotton, tobacco or sugarcane, would, probably starve upon them; but we find that they suit the Tea-plant perfectly. It is a striking coincidence that we should find our tea soils and those of China so exactly alike.” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 17) Through this geological – geographical comparison, the conclusion highlights that the tea plant of Assam, “is not to be

looked upon as *an alien estranged from its own climate, but as an indigenous plant, neglected, it is true, by man, but in the full enjoyment from nature* (emphasis in original) of all those peculiar conditions on which its properties will be found, under proper management, to depend” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 19).

The memoir also highlights that by 1836, discussions were already afoot about the possibility of Assam tea as “potable tea”, i.e. a “tea of commerce”. Referring to the remarks of Wallich, and to his correspondences with Jenkins, the memoir notes how Wallich thought, “No scheme was ever entered upon with such a progressive accumulation of favourable and confirmatory circumstances, as our Tea scheme,” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 27) and also that Jenkins had mentioned to him (Wallich), “under proper treatment they would be made to yield a very valuable supply of potable Tea, which would *before long repay all the expenses of the preliminary trials* (emphasis in original).” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 28) But it was also around that time, as the memoir points out to its intended readers and the company shareholders, that it became clear that the future of tea production in Assam would be through “private enterprise”. For example, the memoir notes that the Court of Directors of the East India Company clearly pointed out by 1837 that, “The carrying out of the experiment into practice upon such a scale as to render the production of the article a mercantile speculation, was never contemplated by government, whose part will be *abundantly fulfilled* (emphasis in original) as soon as the practicability of the plan is established” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 33).

The memoir continues, “Francis Jenkins had pointed to the role of private enterprise in this regard even more emphatically. For example, he writes, ‘Should our teas be considered of good marketable qualities, *I hope some capitalists in England will join to farm our tea-tracks* (emphasis in original). The extent of country over which the Tea-plants have been discovered to grow, is so great, that the manufacture of Tea might at once commence on the largest scale; and it is very important that this should be generally known, for the promise it gives of *immediate return will aid much to encourage capitalists to embark in a speculation for the manufacture of Tea in Assam* (emphasis in original).’” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 34-35) Further, the tea chests from Assam that were sent to London for auction in 1838 also established in what way Assam tea would differ from Chinese green tea in the global tea market. As the memoir notes, “The public want something that will taste through hard water, sugar, and milk, and therefore they must have a stronger Tea. The second, Pekoe-kind is a Tea most valuable to this country.... The Tea that would be most used would be that which would stand *two liquorings* (emphasis in original), and cost least in the market. From the trials given to the Tea from Assam, it certainly bears two liquorings, far better than many of the articles from China, and the probable cost of importation will give it the preference in point of price to the consumer” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 36-37).

Early next year, 1839, the Assam Company is formed. It is the first tea company of British India. In this regard, while outlaying the moment of its establishment, the memoir notes, “It was thus apparent that the Court of Directors, the Board of Control, the Supreme Government of India, the Tea Committee at Calcutta, and all other parties most conversant with the subject, concur in opinion that the cultivation of the plant,

and the manufacture and importation of Tea from Assam should become a matter of *private adventure* (emphasis in original). The Assam Company was accordingly formed in the month of February last, with a present capital of £500,000 in 10,000 shares of £50 each: 8000 shares were set aside for allotment in England, and 2000 for allotment in India.” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 37) Addressing the shareholders and those interested in the Company, while the memoir notes, “Parties are not to expect an *immediate* (emphasis in original) return of exorbitant profit,” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 38) it also highlights that, “the undertaking is one of a national character, and equally important to public as to private interests.” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 39) Interestingly, the memoir also points out, “Thus the Assam Company has been associated for the promotion of a distant commercial enterprise, to which individual capital alone cannot at first be conveniently applied” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 39). Finally, with regard to the name of the Company, the memoir notes that while tea is its main concern, Assam has other resources as well, and therefore, “These facts justify the Company in assuming the general designation of Assam Company, rather than restricting it to the Assam *Tea* (emphasis in original) Company, though that article will most probably form the chief part of their operations” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 15-16).

As a memoir addressed to the shareholders of the newly formed Assam Company, as well as others interested in such initiatives, the last section (Chapter III) of the memoir sums up the relation between Assam (i.e. the eastern frontier), the British Indian empire and capitalists such as the Company itself, at a global scale. For example, the memoir notes that in the 1830s, “When our advanced position in the eastern frontier is compared to with what we occupied before the Burmese war, we perceive the great degree of security which our acquisitions have given to our ancient possessions, a security they never before enjoyed. A consolidation of the territories, embracing the several states of Assam, Cachar, Jyntiah, Cossyah, and Araccan, has materially strengthened the British frontiers, which, as long as they remained subjected to weak and imbecile rulers of their native provinces, constantly exposed us to the danger of collision with the ambitious power beyond them. A spirit of enterprise has been awakened, already productive of a most extraordinary revival and increase of commercial pursuits” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 52-53).

In fact, looking into the future, the memoir notes, “There is sufficient to warrant the expectation that British skill and enterprise will find new and ample fields in communications, opening not merely with Assam, and the neighbouring countries, but with China, through the province of Yunnan” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 54). Therefore, the memoir notes, “if such shall be the result of the extension of the British influence over the numerous tribes and nation that dwell on our eastern frontier,” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 55) it would lead to these peoples’ recollection of their own violent and debased past fading away, and, “elevating them to that higher station in the intellectual and moral world, upon which the favoured inhabitant of Europe now stands.” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 55) One may argue that the memoir’s conclusion also takes one back to the very opening paragraph of the memoir, addressed to the shareholders of the Company that began with the question, “Where is Assam?” (Assam: Sketch, 1839: 1) As the rest of the memoir tries to show, the answer to the question, in its view, lay in freeing the region from its past or the sense of past that its “natives” are supposed to

be living with, and inventing for it a new history. In other words, what we are witness to is a history at a global scale, and engineered through a new process, namely that of a commodity: the “tea of commerce”.

The preceding discussion highlights a point of central significance in the capitalist-imperialist logic. The point is that, while the commodity history of capitalism is founded on a global scale of manufacture and circulation, actualising the scale involves reorganising (or reinventing) the meaning of society and place at the local level as well. The disruptions produced by these processes can manifest in a range of people’s struggles. However, it does not distract capitalism and colonialism from pursuing the above principle of its constitution. For example, as early as 1839, Charles A. Bruce writes in his Report on tea in Assam, “It is therefore important for us to look well to our Eastern frontier, on account of our capability to extend our tea cultivation in that direction” (Bruce (1839)1840: 36-37).⁵ And a few years later, in 1842, referring to the Singpho areas on the Assam-Burma frontier, Francis Jenkins points out, “Obedience to our authority has been widely and rapidly extended on this frontier of late. . . . The consequences are beginning to be felt in the advance of traders to the most distant frontier villages, and the confidence with which European gentlemen have been lately residing amongst the Singphos employed in cultivating the fine tea plantations of Koonjo and Jogundoo; and I feel assured that by the establishment of a strong post at Ningroo, by opening out roads to it from Jeypore and Rungagora, and by occasional residence there during the cold season of the Political Agent or other officer, that the whole of these eastern districts will soon be reduced to entire submission, and from having been never-ceasing causes of watchfulness, expense, and anxiety, will begin to add to the productive resources and wealth of the province, and from giving us the means of commanding the passes towards Ava, will contribute to our military strength and political supremacy.” (Hill Tracks (1873), 1978: 255-256) In fact, Charles Bruce had remarked that expansion of Assam tea would, “enrich our own dominions, and pull down the haughty pride of China” (Bruce, 1839: 38).

There is already a substantial body of scholarship on the history of tea and empire in British Assam (Guha, 2014; Barpujari, 2007; Antrobus, 1957; Sharma, 2012; Behal, 2014; Hilaly, 2016: 55-62, Varma, 2016, Carlson, 2022). As such, the objective behind using the above example is only to highlight that the archival records are transparent about the integral relation between empire and capital when it comes to tea and frontier making in British Assam (which included plains, foothills, and highlands in this case). Such records also show that even in this formative period of colonialism in the region, incoherence was hardly the essence of colonial institutions, or in the minds of the colonial agents. In fact, a few recent studies have perceptively highlighted some of these dimensions, especially how accumulation of power and capital entangled and transformed spaces across plains, foothills and highlands as far as tea is concerned. Mainly focusing on the Patkai foothills and highlands, they illustrate the complex relations between the tea and coal companies on the one hand, and the Patkai Nagas on the other hand. This complex relation was in terms of new ideas of wealth, property (land), significance of writing connected to commerce, and the transformation of landscape. Thus, by the 1870s, the world of the Patkai Nagas was already changing as a result of their engagement with tea and coal companies in the area (Kar, 2016: 41-67).

Such transformations entailed circulations (of money, goods, and people). In this regard, colonial reports also highlight how circulations had come to mediate the changing world of the Patkai Nagas (Porter, 1930; Porter, 1933).⁶ Interestingly, while such transformations became possible due to conditions made possible by the colonial state, the colonial reports themselves would often discourse how such circulations could be monitored and regulated through periodic show of strength (military or political) or by display of polite but firm goodwill.

The point here is not that such transformations meant the elimination of pre-colonial socio-economic or political institutions. Rather, the point is how, from the vantage point of empire, accumulation of power and capital as a conjoined process could appropriate existing social-economic-political forms and institutions towards the reproduction of empire and capital in these areas. Something similar can also be seen in the case of the Himalayan foothills and its adjoining highlands. For example, in the case of the Sadiya and the Balipara Frontier tracts, one can find the existence of different modes of production – peasant, plantation and tribal modes of production – but in their combinations. At a practical level, it meant how hill tribes, Marwari shops, tea plantations, and the local peasants were entangled in the frontier lifeworld. But on the other hand, it was also through this entanglement that imperial accumulation of power and capital was effected.⁷ For example, the colonial Apatani expedition of 1896, especially how the traditional social and village ties between the Apatanis, Nyishis and the Miris became entangled in the processes of foothill tea plantations of the colonial Lakhimpur district and how the ensuing violence of this entanglement marked the colonial state registering its power in these highlands, illustrates both the complexity of the entanglement as well as how empire and capital operates to realise its rationale (Blackburn, 2008: 129-133).

In this context, circulatory networks become extremely meaningful and revealing when they are located in the context of accumulation of imperial power and capital. It shows what comprises the basis of the reproduction of circulation at a global scale, though it requires to be engendered locally. Thus, in terms of circulatory networks, the “tea of commerce” was already becoming a part of a global circulation of capital and goods by the 1840s. In a couple of decades, it would also become part of a global circulatory network of indentured labour. In turn, these circulatory networks would penetrate or impact across the different geographies of the region. In this regard, whether it be the institutions or the circulatory networks, they hinged on the actuality of accumulation and reproduction of power and capital in the region, not on their liminality.

In fact, some of the recent studies on circulatory networks in the highlands of the region have noted how the goods (such as, firearms) can be better understood as part of a process of manufacture, sale and circulation that connected Europe, South Asia and Southeast Asia of the times (Dzuvichu, 2021: 416-435). Colonial Northeast India provides a vivid illustration of how different geographies and societies (of a frontier) could become structured into the process. As such, the colonial concerns at times over the networks seemingly exceeding the limits of colonial surveillance and control should not distract us from the fact that the very underlying rationale of these networks was also about deepening and widening the penetration of the process of accumulation

of power and capital in different social and geographical directions. In this respect, it is also important to recognise that it is rather an entirely different question whether a community perceives or experiences the socio-economic implications of the process through a consciousness of its rationale, i.e., cognition, in as many words.

Even with regard to the “tea of commerce”, recent studies on the peasants of the Brahmaputra valley (Saikia, 2014) and on the tribes of the Patkai highlands (Kar, 2016: 41-67) have noted that the issue is not whether such communities perceive or experience the socio-economic implications of the “tea of commerce”, or localises it, through a consciousness of the rationale. Rather, the question needs to be reversed. That is, one needs to enquire how this rationale shapes the condition, consciousness and practices of such communities which may or may not directly pertain to “tea of commerce” only but may come to exist at more wide-ranging and complex levels. Such as, as already noted, new ideas and practices of land, wealth, power and resource. In fact, this point that how a worldwide process is perceived or experienced at the local level does not take away anything from the reality of the worldwide process was remarkably captured in the quotation of a poem that the 1839 memoir of the Assam Company used. The memoir, while discussing with the shareholders questions, such as, “Where is Assam?” (a question the memoir posed) and what would Assam tea mean, cited and repurposed the following lines from John Dyer’s poem (*The Fleece: A Poem*, Book IV, 1757) for its own context:

The whole globe
Is now of commerce made the scene immense.
Nor is there wheel in the machine of trade,
Which Leeds or Cairo, Lima or Bombay
Helps not with harmony to turn around,
Though all unconscious of the union act.

(Assam: Sketch, 1839: 54)

This clarity in the mind of the Assam Company, one may argue, is what coherence of empire and a range of networks around capital engenders. It is the logic of reasoning of an imperial company whose cultivation and manufacture of a commodity is taking place far away from the London Stock market, and whose commodity would be traveling to different destinations of the world, including Britain.

With regard to the colonial Northeast India, the ideas of incoherence of empire and circulatory networks in the recent scholarship have directed our attention to another important consideration. Such as, while examining the colonial context, it helps to make a distinction between the forms of dominant colonial reality and others which may or may not be its effects, but are nevertheless forms which cannot be understood in isolation from the dominant ones. For example, all circulatory networks need not be an outcome of colonialism and capitalism. They can pre-exist these processes. At the same time, it is always possible that a subject can exist in different subject conditions under given situations (socio-economic, political and cultural), and that these different subject conditions are not per se produced by the logic of empire and capital. However, colonial institutions and their socio-economic impact comprise the dominant forms of

reality during the period, while the other forms become entangled in the nature and effects of the dominant forms. In this regard, a few of such instances have been already pointed out –the engagement of the Patkai Nagas with the tea and mineral companies, and the transformations that such engagement introduced in their world, or how the Sadiya and Balipara Frontier tracts were characterised by the entanglement (i.e., combinations) of different socio-economic processes (peasant, plantation, tribal).

Another interesting instance in this regard can be gleaned from the memoir of Purnakanta Buragohain, an Assamese trader who traded between Assam and Burma between the 1930s and the early 1940s (Buragohain 2021). His areas of business operation and travel in Burma included the Hukawng valley, the Bhamo area, and the Kachin highlands, including the borders of Yunnan. Buragohain points out that in terms of networks of trade (i.e., routes, means of transport, institutions such as the network of police and postal stations, and market), there were those which were created under British rule in Assam and Burma, and it were these networks that made his business and travel possible. But in the process of his business and travel, he also came across networks which had an older history, such as elephant catching by Assamese traders in the Hukawng valley of Burma. These older networks comprising of routes, men, and objects of trade (the elephant) continued in the colonial period too. In terms of social processes, Buragohain points out that there were new social patterns along the borders of the Chin areas till the Hukawng valley of Burma. This is due to the settlement of large numbers of former soldiers of the colonial army and the colonial military police, either with their families or through inter-marriage with local women, along these areas. However, there were also villages along these areas as well as in Bhamo and occasionally in the Kachin highlands which were the result of older pre-colonial histories of mobilities and settlement of people from the region in Burma. Though these villages now viewed themselves as belonging to Burma, the older histories were still part of their historical memory.

Such details of Buragohain's memoir highlight an important point, that colonial institutions or the socio-economic processes and networks that unfolded under colonial rule did not comprise the only forms of reality in these areas. There were other forms of reality too, those with different or older histories. But across the valleys and highlands of the Assam-Burma frontier, it was colonial institutions, and socio-economic processes and networks connected to colonialism that constituted the dominant mode. The other modes, despite their different and older histories, become entangled in the reproduction of the dominant colonial mode. In other words, what we are witness to is the combination of the different modes, but in a manner that reproduces the dominance of the colonial mode (for a discussion on this point, also see, Baruah, 2024). Such an understanding not only allows one to analytically overcome the appearance of "incoherence" or liminality of empire in the frontiers, but also makes it possible to read circulatory networks in terms of regimes (i.e., there is a certain dominant location of power) of network under given historical conditions, not as an open-ended process or flow. Such an understanding also alerts us to the fact that empire and capital of the nineteenth-till-mid-twentieth centuries were not illusory to the lived realities of the people of the region. Rather, they had a concrete reality. But it was a reality that needs to be understood in terms of the complex ways through which accumulation of power

and capital became possible and materialised.

Conclusion

As mentioned earlier, with regard to highlands of the region there are actually two frameworks in recent studies – one of empire’s incoherence and in that sense circulation, and the other of empire’s coherence (though disguised or discoursed by the colonial state in languages of liminality) and circulation as part of that regime. But what the preceding discussion on the colonial period has highlighted is that just as the plains during the period cannot be essentialised in general, highlands too cannot be essentialised. For example, as recent studies have argued, there were highland areas which could fit into the framework of incoherence of empire, and circulation in that respect. Yet, there were also highland areas which were fundamentally entangled in colonial processes. In the latter cases, circulation too carried a different meaning, one which is more about how global processes could become engendered at local levels due to it, or through it. Further, the preceding discussion has also highlighted that as far as colonial Northeast India is concerned, rather than a given geographical form per se as our basis to understand empire it might be more helpful to examine how empire and capital actually comprised a complex process that could tie (i.e., entangle) different geographies in a wider and deeper logic – accumulation of power and capital, a logic inherently global in character and practice. In this respect, in terms of existing studies as well as in terms of the archival resources available, tea and minerals perhaps provide one of the most compelling illustrations of how this logic could conceive, and operate to realise itself.

Endnotes

¹ Though not about capital, Mandy Sadan had clearly pointed out that British empire’s expansion in the region was clear sighted from the beginning. See, Sadan, 2013.

² Hannah Arendt had very perceptively noted, “never-ending accumulation of power necessary for the protection of a never-ending accumulation of capital.” (Arendt, (1951)2017: 186).

³ The setting up of the Tea Committee in 1834 was an important concrete step by the British government on the tea question in India. While the initial interest of the government was not in Assam, it was around 1836 that the government interest in Assam began to acquire significance. By 1838, there were a few tea plantations that were operational through the government initiative. They were at Chabua, Tingri and Dinjoy.

⁴ This is a point which Charles A. Bruce also makes in Report (1839) on tea in Assam, especially how the different societies in Upper Assam were in the practice of planting and drinking tea, though in a manner different from the manufacture of tea for the British market. For example, he wrote, “A Dewaniah who assisted me to hunt out these tracts, and who was well acquainted with the leaf, as he had been in the habit of drinking tea during his residence with the Singphoes, informed me that he had seen a large tract of Tea plants on the Naga mountains, a day’s journey west of *Cheridoo*. I have no reason to doubt the veracity of this man.” (Bruce, 1840: 2).

⁵ This observation was in the context of violent anti-colonial wars (such as, waged by

the Singphoes, the Muttacks, etc.) throughout the area in the late 1830s.

⁶ Also see, Stoppage of rail-thefts by the Trans-Patkai Ranghang Nagas, 1929, Appointment, Political, Pol/162-190/29, Assam State Archives, Guwahati, Assam.

⁷ Nil 1709-1748/1924, 1924, Political B, Assam State Archives, Guwahati, Assam. Also see, Administration Report Part IIB, Report on the Administration of the Province of Assam for the Year 1898-99, p. 17.

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